

ISic0404

Sarcophagus of Adelpia

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

sarcophagus

Editor

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2017

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Found 12 June 1872 in the

Coordinates

37.0767995, 15.2848558

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 864

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. hic Adelfia c(larissima) f(emina)
2. posita conpar
3. Baleri comitis

Apparatus

IC with no space for initial H

Translation (en)

Here is laid to rest Adelfia, lady of senatorial rank, wife of the Count Valerius

Translation (it)

Qui è deposta Adelfia clarissima femina moglie del conte Valerio

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491615
EDCS 21900445

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